

A CRITICAL STUDY OF SWASTHA CHATUSHKA W.S.R TO USE OF TANTRAYUKTIS**Dr. Sudha*¹, Dr. Shilpi², Dr. Sarla³, Dr. Pradeep Kumar Sachan⁴**¹P.G Scholar, Department of Samhita Evam Siddhant, State Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Lucknow, Mahayogi Guru Gorakhnath AYUSH University, Gorakhpur- 273306, India.²P.G Scholar, Department of Samhita Evam Siddhant, State Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Lucknow, Mahayogi Guru Gorakhnath AYUSH University, Gorakhpur- 273306, India.³Reader & H.O.D., Department of Samhita Evam Siddhant, State Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Lucknow, Mahayogi Guru Gorakhnath AYUSH University, Gorakhpur- 273306, India.⁴Prof. & H.O.D., Department of Samhita Evam Siddhant, State Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Lucknow, Mahayogi Guru Gorakhnath AYUSH University, Gorakhpur- 273306, India.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Sudha**

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ABSTRACT

Charaka Samhita is reputed to be the most ancient, comprehensive, authoritative, original text. The *Samhita* is rich in principles. We can live a healthy life by following those principles. To understand these principles, it is essential for us to have knowledge of *Tantrayuktis*. *Charaka Samhita* has eight sections and one hundred twenty chapters. Sutra sthana is foremost among the eight *sthanas*. It is divided into seven *Chatushka*. *Swastha chatushka* holds the second position among seven *chatushkas*, including procedures essential for the maintenance of health. The chapter included in *Swastha Chatushka* gives more importance to the maintenance of both physical and mental health. By using *Tantrayuktis*, we understand the depth of knowledge of *Swastha chatushka* and their application in a proper way.

KEYWORDS: *Swastha chatushka, Dinacharya, Ritucharya, Tantrayuktis.***INTRODUCTION**

rnk;qosZn;rhR;k;qosZn%^[1][Cha.su.30/23]
vk;qjflEu~ fo|rs] vusu ok.;qfoZUnfUr* bR;k;qosZn%^[2]
[Su.su 1/26]

The scriptures which give the knowledge about age is called *Ayurveda*. *Ayurveda* is one of the oldest medical systems in the world. *Ayurveda* means knowledge related to life. *Ayurveda* is the branch of science which keeps human body healthy, getting rid of disease or reducing it and increasing the life span. *Charaka Samhita* is a fundamental text of ayurveda written by *Acharya Charaka*. It has eight sections and one hundred twenty chapters. It explains the basic principles of ayurvedic science of living and also provides clinical approach to treat the diseases. The *Sutrasthana* of *Charaka Samhita* is divided in to seven *Chatushka* and *Sangraha dwya*.^[3]

1-Bhesaja *Chatushka*
2-Swastha *Chatushka*

3-Nirdesh *Chatushka*
4-kalpna *Chatushka*
5-Roga *Chatushka*
6-Yojana *Chatushka*
7-Annapana *Chatushka*
8-Sangraha *Dwya*

To describe the matters of *Sutrasthana* by using *Chatushka* is a sign of excellent scientific thinking. *Acharya* told that all *Chatushka* have their own importance. *Charaka Samhita* has mention *chatushka* word with a specific term 'MAHA ARTHA'. To understand the *Swastha chatushka* well, there is a need to read the *Tantrayuktis* because with time, the specific knowledge also keeps on changing maximum facts have been published by the *Acharyas* in minimum words, but the *Acharyas* knew how to understand the deep topics of this *Shashtra*. Hence, they have created a key called

Tantrayukti it opens the secrets of the *Shastra*. Thus, if *shastra* is a closed box, then *Tantrayukti* is its key without the key of *Tantrayukti*, the box of *Shastra* cannot be opened. They help bridge the gap between *Shastra gyan* and *yukti gyan*, making it easier to apply the teaching of *Samhitas* in clinical and day to day *Ayurvedic* practice. Thus, they bring clarity and usefulness to the rich literature of *Ayurveda*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

To study the topics mentioned in the *Swastha chatushka*, the classical *Ayurvedic* literature especially *Charaka Samhita* and the opinions of the commentators have been reviewed. To live a healthy life, the *Acharya* has explained daily routine, seasonal regimen, good habits and diet and how to maintain a balance in life style. Because it is difficult to know what we do and don't. In these chapters all the instructions, benefits and harms are explained. After reading the chapters of the *Swastha chatushka* thoroughly and then understand the *Tantrayuktis*. By the *Tantrayuktis* how the *Acharya* has written *Swastha chatushka* and all four chapters are link to each other has been studied. An analytical study of *Swastha chatushka* has been done through *Tantrayukti*. *Swastha chatushka* has been explained here by analyzing which *Tantrayukti* has been used by the *Acharya*.

SWASTHA CHATUSHKA

Swastha chatushka is second in the order of seven *Chatushka*. This *Chatushka* comes after *Bhesaja chatushka* and define the objectives of *Ayurveda* i. *LoLFkL*; *LokLFj*{*k.ke*^[4] but it also for *vrqjL*; *fodkjç'keua p*^[5] Because *Chikitsa* in *Ayurveda* is to bring to the status of *dhatu samya* and *swasthya* is the state of *dhatu samaya*.^[6]

In today's time, people think about eating good food but don't think about the quantity in which it should be taken. If a person consumes food after considering its quantity, then he can avoid diseases caused due to intake of food in less or excess quantity. To remain healthy, *Acharya* has prescribed *Swastha chatushka* which includes the following chapters.

1. *Matrashitiyadhyaya*
2. *Tasyashitiyaadhaya*
3. *Navegandharaniya*
4. *Indriyopkramniya*

Under the *Swastha Chatushka*, along with description of the following important topics are.

1. *Aharamatra*
2. *Nandit aahara*
3. *Nitya sevaniye aahara*
4. *Swasthavrutta acharna*
5. *Aadana or visarga kaala*
6. *Satmya and okasatmya*
7. *Adharaniye vega and dharniye vega*
8. *Vyaymvarnana*
9. *Hit-ahit aahara sevana evam tyaga vidhi by padamshika krama*

10. *Sharirika prakruti*
11. *Dadhi seven niyam*
12. *Panchapanchak*
13. *Mana its guna*
14. *Panch gnanendriya*
15. *Sadvritta acharana*

The order of the chapters gives us a scientific thought stream that in this *Chatushka* each four these chapters connected together and arranged logically. *Matrashitiyadhyaya* deals with the basic needs of a human being to be healthy. First part of this chapters helps us to understand about healthy ways of eating and its beneficial effect, the next part of the chapters describes the *SWASTHVRIT*. Food is required for the natural functions of the human body. If food is not taken in proper quantity, health cannot remain in its natural form, for the maintenance of health food should be taken in appropriate quantity is one of the most important factors - ek=k'kh L;kr~ A vkgkjek=k iqujfXucykisf{k.kh^[7] [Cha.su.5/3] |

A person must eat food in appropriate quantity because the quantity of food depends on *jatharagni*. Food consumed in appropriate quantity increases strength, happiness and life span. But food consumed in proper quantity also depends upon seasonal harmony. Therefore, to remove this doubt, *Tasyashitiya* chapter is being prescribed. According to *Charaka* the chapter shows the ways of living according to the nature. In the two chapters of *Swastha chatushka* primarily diet and secondarily behaviour related to the healthy lifestyles regarding *ritucharya* have been described. *Navegandharaniya* is the third chapter of this *Chatushka*. The preventive aspects of health are well outlined here. After consuming healthy food, when it gets properly transformed in to *ras*, *rakta* etc. from its essence and gets excreted from the body in the form of faeces and urine etc, then health remains good. If the flow of stool, urine etc. is retained then health cannot maintain even after taking healthy diet. It has been said that the dietary habit have been explained in the previous three chapters. Now the rest of the behavioural habits and the avoidance of *atiyoga*, *ayoga* and *mithyayoga* of *indriyas* and *mana* have been described in the *indriyopkramniya* chapter, being related to *panch panchak* and *sadvritt*, *indriyopkramniya* is unique in itself. This chapter is the conducting chapter of *swastha chatushka*.

MATRASHITIYE ADHAYAYA

This chapter deals with essential basic needs of a human being to be healthy. food supports life, without food the body cannot exist. Taking a balance diet and right quantity of food keeps our health in better condition. *Acharya Charaka* provides a specific daily pattern to be followed in order to maintain a state of balance. Here many options related food put forward on a regular basis as they both prevent the onset of sickness and retain wellness. Second part of this chapter to understand about healthy way of living/*dinnacharya*. Lifestyle of an

individual can be considered as a scale of measurement of health. Because of faulty lifestyle many physical and mental disorders are raising their heads in surrounding. Healthy lifestyles with good habits may lead to excellent

health. A healthy lifestyle helps in prevention of many diseases. Back in the ancient period our acharyas are well known by these facts and they illustrate steps for healthy living.

Table No. 1: Dincharya according to Acharya Charaka.

DINCHARYA	PREVENTION AND HEALTH PROMOTION
Malotsarga (voiding the excrements)	Increase digestive power and prevent lower GIT infections.
Achaman (shipping of water)	Prevent eye infection.
Dantdhavan (brushing of teeth)	Brings freshness, takes away bad odour and coating on teeth.
Jihwa nirlekhan	Remove bad taste, odour, cures oedma, stiffness of tongue and improves taste
Netra prakshalana	Purifies eyes and prevent Akshi dosha.
Anjanna (collyrium)	Clear vision, prevent excessive lacrymation, promote proper functioning and purity of eyes.
Nasya	Prevent early ageing signs and gives prominent and good looking skin.
Gandusha (mouth wash)	Enhance mandible strength, voice resonance, face nourishment, taste sensation and gives good taste.
Dhoompana (medicated smoke)	Cleanses the respiratory track, oral cavity and pharynx
Abhyanga (oily massage)	Mitigates <i>vata</i> , promote strength, sleep, growth and firmness of the hair.
Vyayama (exercise)	Lightness in body, increased capacity to work, keen appetite, reduction of body fat.
Udvardhana (dry massage)	Liquifies fat, makes body part firm and is best for healthy skin.
Snana (bath)	Improves appetite, sexual vigor, life span and strength.
Chhaurkarma	Enhances brightness, increases life span and increases strength.
Vastradharana	Enhance charm and personality, promotes longevity, prevents bad luck and brings about pleasure.

TASYASHITIYA ADHYAYA

Ritu vibhaga for *swasthavritta* plan firstly a year/*samvatsara* is divided in to six parts according to a season or climate change. The season from *sisira* to *Grishma* considered as *udnagayana* or *adana kaala*.^[8] Season from *Varsha* to *Hemanta* considered as *visarga kaala*.^[9] In this chapter Acharya describe *bala* and *agni* according to *kaala*, *sadritucharya*, *satmya* is also described in this chapter. The term *satmya* denotes in different meaning i.e adaptation, suitable habitat wholesome diet and lifestyles habituation [*satmya*] that suits the itself. *Satmya* and *upashya* have the same meaning thus, *satmya* is integral part of preservation of health and treatment.

NAVEGANDHARANIYA ADHYAYA

In this chapter acharya explain about 13 *adharniya vega*^[10] and disease caused by holding up these *vega/urges* and their treatment. *Dharniya vega*.^[11] concerned with mental activities, emotions should be controlled. These are categorized by *Acharya Charaka* as *manas vega* [urges of mind], *vachika vega* [urges of speech], *kayak vega* [urges of the body]. These activities should be controlled to obtain *punya* [virtue]. Obtaining *punya* the person enjoys *dharma*, *Artha* and *kama* and also produce these.

Table No. 2: Adharneeey Vegas (Suppression of Natural Urges)^[8]

S.No.	ADHARNEEYA VEGAS	DISEASES MANIFESTED
1.	Mutra vega rodha	Pain in urinary bladder and penis, painful micturition, groins bulging.
2.	Purish vega rodha	No movement of flatus and faeces, large intestinal pain.
3.	Sukra vega rodha	Pain in penis and testis, malaise, no movement of urine.
4.	Adhovata vega rodha	Elimination of faeces, urine and flatus, pain and exhaustion.
5.	Chhardi vega rodha	Itching, loss of taste, anemia, fever, leprosy.
6.	Kshavathu vega rodha	Neck rigidity, headache, facial paralysis, disability of sense organs.
7.	Jrambha vega rodha	Convulsions, loss of tactile sensation, shivering.
8.	Kshuda vega rodha	Emaciation, malaise, taste loss and dizziness.
9.	Pipasa vega rodha	Dryness of throat and mouth, deafness, exertion, chest discomfort.
10.	Vaspa vega rodha	Dryness of throat and mouth, deafness, exertion, chest discomfort.
11.	Nidra vega rodha	Excessive yawning, malaise, stupor, headache,
12.	Udgara vega rodha	Hiccup, dyspnoea, shivering, feeling of obstruction in the region of heart.
13.	Sramasvasa rodha	Abdominal tumor, heart diseases, fainting.

INDRIOPAKRAMANIYA AADHYAYA

This is final most distinctive chapter of *Swastha chatushka*, and it address the intellect and senses as well as ethical standard for behaviour and conduct. The system of *indriya panchapanchaka* [five components related to five *indriyas*] in which the senses act as instruments for the mind to express itself as well as for the soul to acquire knowledge. Senses are controlled by the mind, which is further controlled by buddhi [intellect] and ultimately by *atma* [soul]. When there is *samayoga* of these four. It leads one towards proper health and on the other hand *hina*, *mithya*, *atiyoga* misguides one's intellect resulting in ill health. *Sadvritta* or ethical observances consist of self control and proper activities. It includes self reliance, auto suggestions *kayaka*, *vachika*, *manasika*, and all sorts of activities in daily life along ability to discern and exercise control over *dharaniya* and *adharaniya vega's*. so, the principles of good conducts [*sadvritta*] aim to preserve all dimensions of health.

TANTRAYUKTI

Tantra [treatise] is that by which the body can be protected and treated. *Yukti* are the reasonable tools used for proper planning, assessment and gaining of true knowledge by analyzing multiple factors using intelligence. The learning tools used for decorating and assessing the concepts mentioned in the *tantra* is called as *Tantrayukti*. Ayurvedic classics have been written by the using *Tantrayukti* by removing *tantradasha* and by applying *tantraguna* [qualities of a good treatise]. Another utility of *Tantrayukti* is the proper arrangement of words in a sentence and its exact meaning. Even the topics not mentioned clearly can be revealed, the concise topics can be elaborated, and hidden meanings can be brought in to limelight.

DERIVATION OF TANTRA

Tantra – tan + shtran

Tan – 'tanuvistare' [elaborate or expand].

Shtran- tooler instrument or devices.

Thus, tantra means an ability to get expanded as per the necessity.

DEFINITION OF TANTRA

Tantra is that treatise which with holds all the complications and writing of all subject matters deal in ayurveda. According to Acharya Charaka, the word tantra is a synonym of shastra or treatise. Shastra i.e. a treatise or textbook of reference or a literature or a scientific paper would be called an ideal tool of

comprehensive knowledge. =k;rs 'kjhjeususfr rU=a 'kkL=a fpdfRlk p [Su.su.65/2 Dalhana].

Tantra has two meanings as per *Acharya Dalhana*. It is the science that helps us to protect the body and it is also the science which helps us in treating the diseased body.

According to *Acharya Arundutta*, tantra is that by which the body can be protected. Thus, *tantra* is that science which gives us knowledge on how to protect and treat our body.

DERIVATION OF YUKTI

Yukti- yojana = derived from *yujir dhatu*.

DEFINITION OF YUKTI

Yukti= *yojana* [union], *Upaya*[plan], *Nyaya* [reasonable application], *Neeti* [reasonable practice].

;qfä'p ;kstk ;k rq ;qT;rs^[13] [Cha.su.26/31] According to *Acharya Charaka*, *yukti* is the proper and reasonable application of the things and ideas. If any planning is not up to the mark, it is not thought to be *yukti*.

cqf)% i';fr;k Hkkoku~ cgqdkj.k;ksxtku~

;qfäL=dkyk lk Ks;k f=oxZ% lk/rs ;;k^[14] [Cha.su.11/25]

Yukti is also defined as the intelligence necessary for perception of knowledge. It gives knowledge about *Trikala*- past, present, and future and *Trivarga – Dharma* [righteousness in life], *Artha* [materialistic wealth] and *Kama* [desires in life]. Thus, *yukti* means proper planning, assessment or reasoning and gaining of true knowledge by analyzing multiple factors using intelligence.

DEFINITION OF TANTRAYUKTI

=k;rs 'kjhjeususfr rU=a 'kkL=a fpdfRlk] p] rL; ;qä;ks ;kstkLrU=;qä;%^[15] [Su.su.65/2 dalhana] In *Samhita*,

tantra and *yukti* are both independent. *Tantra* means conceptual textual knowledge, and *yukti* means practical applications. All commentators of *Samhita* explain the *Tantrayukti* word as *yuktis* of the tantra. They are conjugated with the words *yukti* of tantra, therefore, *yukti* in *tantra* is *Tantrayukti*. The principal word *Tantrayukti* means methods of applications for aggregate concepts in a scientific treatise. *Tantrayuktis* according to acharyas.

Acharya Charaka has described Thirty-six *Tantrayukti*.

Acharya Sushrut Thirty-two *Tantrayukti* has described.

Bhatterharischandra has described Forty types of *Tantrayukti*.

Table No. 3: Name of Tantrayuktis are.

1. Adhikaran	9. Prayojana	17. Anekanta	25. Atitavekshana	33. Vikalpa
2. Yoga	10. Updesha	18. Apvarga	26. Anagatavekshana	34. Pratyutsaar
3. Hetvarth	11. Apdesha	19. Viparyay	27. Swasangahaya	35. Uddhara
4. Padarth	12. Atidesha	20. Purvapaksh	28. Uhya	36. sambhaya
5. Pradesh	13. Arthapatti	21. Vidhaan	29. Samuchaya	37. Pariprasana
6. Uddesha	14. Nirnaya	22. Anumata	30. Nidarshanam	38. Vyakarana

7. Nirvesha	15. Prasang	23. Vyakhyana	31. Nirvachana	39. Vyutkrantabhidhana
8. Vakyashsha	16. Ekanta	24. Samsaya	32. Niyoga	40. Hetu

DISCUSSION

Sutrasthana acts as the Uddesha of Samhita. It is the collection of sutras which are to be applied all over the Samhita. The remaining Sthanas are the mere elaboration of these Chatushka. Chatushka in Sutrasthana of Charaka Samhita is one of the prime and scientific methods applied by the Acharya.

In a Swastha chatushka, there is an Adhikaran tantrayukti in itself. Because for each Swastha chatushka, a specific topic has been explained. The Acharya has written the scripture in such a way that there is no deviation from the subject. He has explained the topic and the authorised subject.

The quantity of food depends on the digestive fire in this verse: ek=k'kh L;kr~ A vkgkjek=k iqujXucykisf{k.kh¹⁶ [Cha.su.5/3] Nirvesha Tantrayukti is used by the acharya through this verse. Acharya has given his point in the form of sutra. Which is elaborated further.

Vyakhanna tantrayukti is used in all the chapters of Swastha chatushka. All the rules related to food can be understood here.

In Tasyasitiya chapter, the Ritucharya describes the seasons stepwise and their diets and lifestyles. Here, using the Vidhaan Tantrayukti, the acharya has shown the sequence, which makes the understanding of the concept clear.

Acharya has given some such instructions which show that we should explain the opposite of this prohibition to us. We get to know from Arthapatti that we should understand its other meaning for example- u uaa nf/k Hkq~thr pkI;?k`r'kdZje~^[17] [Cha.su.7/61] that is, we should consume the opposite of this.

Through Vikalpa Tantrayukti, acharya has told the availability of this in edible foods. If you don't have this then you can use this.

To explain the state of gastric fire during the winter season, Acharya used Nirdarsaan Tantrayukti here so that, everyone can easily understand the condition of gastric fire.

Acharya has explained the benefit of Anjana karma using Nidarsaan Tantrayukti. How the use of Anjana karma gives the nourishment to the eyes. n`f"VfuZjkdqyk Hkkfr fueZys uHklhUnqor~^[18] [Cha.su.5/20]

Acharya has used the Uahye Tantrayukti like in the chapter Matrashitiya, the quantity of food has been mentioned, but the quantity has not been told, hence here

it should be understood by logic as to how much quantity of food will be for someone.

Sadvritt has been described in the chapter Indroyopkrannayie. Here the Nirvesha and Apdesha Tantrayuktis has been used by the Acharya.

other Tantrayuktis were also applied, such as prayojana, viparya, nirnaya, ekanta etc in Swastha chatushka.

In this way Acharya has explained the scriptures in Swastha chatushka using Tantrayukti. the first aim of ayurveda is to achieve the Swastha awastha, so Acharya has tried to understand all the principles mentioned and explain their meaning in this Chatushka using Tantrayukti. If someone gets the knowledge of one scripture, he gets the knowledge of other scriptures also. The knowledge of Tantrayuktis gives us the light of knowledge given in the scripture in the same way as lotus bloom in the sunlight. A house becomes bright in the darkness by lighting a lamp. In the same way, the knowledge of Tantrayukti illuminate the purpose and deep meaning of the scriptures.

CONCLUSION

We can achieve the first objectives of Ayurveda through the Swastha chatushka. Every person can achieve health and longevity through Swastha chatushka. Samhitas are written in the form of sutras. The commentators tried to explain them by using Tantrayukti. The scriptures become understandable by using Tantrayukti. The general public knows the general regimen related to food, code of conduct, but no one knows the specific regimen. Therefore, it is very important to understand the principles of the Swastha chatushka. This is possible only when we have the knowledge of Tantrayuktis.

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